

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ORIGIN OF DESTRUCTIVE BEHAVIOR IN ADOLESCENTS.

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Abstract: This article provides information on characteristics of adolescent crisis and forms of destructive behavior.

Keywords: destructive behavior, personality formation, pessimist, psychosomatic changes, imitation

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The main characteristic of adolescence is the transition from childhood to adulthood. This period is a period of sharp acceleration of physiological development and sexualization. This period is characterized by the manifestation of negative personality traits by teenagers and their alternation: sometimes they are open to communication, sometimes they are opposite, sometimes they are cheerful, sometimes they are sad, etc. The main goal of a teenager is self-awareness and the formation of similarity (to be like peers).

The transition from adolescence to adulthood is not smooth for everyone. Accordingly, personality formation in adolescence is divided into 3 types (E. Shpranger). For the first type, the period is characterized by a lively, crisis-like transition, like a second birth. Its end is the emergence of a new "I". The second type is characterized by smooth personality formation of the period without strong nervousness. The third type of personality formation is characterized by conscious and active self-education, independent overcoming of worries and objections. Sh. Buhler distinguished mental puberty along with physical puberty and 3 phases within it.

The first is the eve of mental puberty, the following specific signs appear in an 11-12-year-old teenager: restlessness, belligerence, teenage games do not seem interesting to him, and the games of older teenagers will be incomprehensible.

It is followed by a negative (negative) phase, which includes girls aged 11-13 and boys aged 14-16. Rapid excitability and restlessness, sensitiveness, physical and mental weakness, dissatisfaction with oneself are the main characteristics of this period. Therefore, in most teenagers, we can find cases of self-hatred and the

feeling of being alone, alienated, and misunderstood by others as a result. At this time, the teenager becomes very sensitive to contradictions and negative influences, such situations cause aggressive self-defense or passive melancholia in the teenager. The end of the negative phase corresponds to the end of physical maturity.

The positive (positive) phase begins when the adolescent becomes sensitive to the positive sides (aspects) of the environment. Conflicts that arise in the field of interpersonal relations are perceived by teenagers in an emotional and affective way, they hinder the development of a full-fledged person and cause the inefficiency of a teenager's life.

As a result of sexual maturation at this age, significant changes occur in the adolescent's body and psyche. This greatly changes the area of interests of a teenager. In this, we can see two features of the development of interests: on the one hand, the emergence of new interests and inclinations (to read books rich in social life, technology, heroism and adventure; in many people, interest in sports increases), on the other hand, previously established the loss of the system of interests (that's why the negativism, opposite character in it). L.S. According to Vygotsky, it is the combination of these two features that characterizes a strange fact at first glance - the decrease or sometimes complete disappearance of interests. During this destructive phase, a teenager ends his adolescence, which is why L. N. Tolstoy calls this stage "adolescent wilderness." This phase includes pessimism, the breakdown of relationships with the community, the disruption of previously established relationships between teenagers, including friendly relationships, the desire for solitude, a sharp change in attitudes towards other people, disobeying the rules of social behavior. is typical. As a result, most teenagers show themselves in an individual direction. At the same time, the peak of individuality corresponds to middle-aged teenagers, and when it comes to older teenagers, its proportion decreases; they are only interested in the lives of people who are interested in their interests.

The main feature of adolescence is characterized by the intensity of two developments: mental and physical, that is, mental and somatic processes. It is during this period that rapid fatigue, physical weakness, and susceptibility to various diseases can be observed. All these are considered psychosomatic changes, the result of the interdependence of psychic and somatic processes. Most of the adolescent characteristics that are evident are character traits that are visible in his relationship system. These features are called "character accentuation" in psychology.

The issue of character accentuation has been thoroughly studied by many scientists such as M. Kramer, E. Krechmer, K. Leongard, V. Kebrikov, P.B. Gannushkin, V.V. Kovalev, A.E. Lichko. Character accentuation is an extreme

manifestation of certain qualities and sets of qualities, which indicates a variant of the norm bordering on the psychopath. Character accentuation is distinguished by the fact that psychopaths do not have three characteristic features at the same time. These signs are: stability of character over time, generalization in all situations, and social maladaptation. There are open and hidden (latent) forms of character accentuation, which can easily overlap under the influence of such important factors as family upbringing, social environment, professional activity, and physical health. Accentuation of character is formed during adolescence, smoothed and compensated over time. The researchers note that the manifestation of destructive behavior may be related to the problem of character accentuation in adolescents.

Experts say that a number of accentuations in the character can be an impetus for the development of deviant behavior as a result. A very strong expression of the psycho-emotional crisis in adolescence. Usually, in the physiological and psychological development of minors, very strong and sharp internal conflicts arise in a certain period. Not everyone can easily experience such a strong psycho-emotional state. For this reason, the behavior of teenagers in such a period is characterized by tension, irritability, rudeness, and very quick to get upset.

For them, antisocial morality appears as a means of self-expression, of demonstrating one's identity and maturity. [24. 304b]

Adolescents with destructive behavior tend to adopt the norms of behavior, behavior, and attitude of members of the group who are considered important for them. However, the structure of a person with a destructive behavior is formed by the emotional states of fear of losing oneself, not loving someone, isolation, meaninglessness, helplessness, anger and despair. If such a person joins a group of people like him, it is easy for him to forget that his personal situation is intolerable. If they commit a crime together, such a crime is usually directed at members of the community.

Psychologist A.I. Dolgova, who studied juvenile delinquency, said that before committing a crime, there are sharp deviations from the norm in a teenager's behavior. The author distinguished 2 types of normative deviations typical for adolescents with deviant behavior:

- violent and selfish teenagers want to show themselves as strong, responsive and ready to help their peers. But the conclusion of this category of teenagers about the truth is a criminal conclusion. In their character, elements such as selfishness, tyranny, belief in physical strength, favoring non-traditional groups prevail. Distorted characteristics such as loneliness and selfishness are characteristic of selfish categories. All teenage criminals are characterized by the fact that they do not understand and appreciate universal human values, work for the benefit of society, and creative activity. Their interest is focused on accumulating material wealth, "living as they wish", and the principles of "pure conscience".

In the scientific works of psychologists studying destructive teenagers, their general psychological and social characteristics are determined. According to D. I. Feldstein, teenagers with destructive behavior are socially sluggish, aggressive, curious, rude, tend to shed "tears", and many of them are deceitful and irresponsible. According to I.A. Semikasheva's research, the participants of such a group have characteristics similar to parents and respect the group they belong to, not individual people. Such teenagers do not feel responsible for their character and act like everyone else in the public. S.A. Kulakov said that adolescents with such behavior are clients of psychotherapists, they may not have been given a clear diagnosis, but many of their characteristics are normatively disturbed. From the research of N. Yu. Maksimova, it was found that there are the following internal reasons that lead to negative situations in the socio-psychological characteristics of adolescents with difficult upbringing, including: difficult communication with classmates, lack of formation of behavioral norms, social not understanding the value of norms and rules of behavior, denial, inability to imagine the world around as a whole, not taking into account the demands and suggestions of pedagogues, high self-esteem, parents, self lack of social correct development due to disagreement with the teacher. A.E. Lichko said that the socio-psychological characteristics of adolescents are related to the following characteristics typical for this age:

I. Break into groups together with peers. Over time, they become involved in conflicts and adventures that harm them. It's sad that idle teenagers are idle and drink alcohol to cheer themselves up. Some teenagers start drinking out of curiosity to "be like adults" and others to avoid being left behind. They will be not only boys, but also girls.

II. Imitation is always imitating someone. Such teenagers repeat the behavior of their peers or adults. If one of the people around him consumes alcohol or drugs, there will be more imitators. Many teenagers choose movie heroes, actors, musicians as their role models and imitate them. If the character being imitated is a negative character, parents and educators should be prepared for various unpleasant situations. Especially if the person chosen for the example is a real person, he is an alcoholic, a drug addict, or a criminal, then you can expect big problems from him, for example, many drug addicts get involved in various crimes because they need a lot of money.

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IV. Negative reaction (opposite feeling). A typical feeling for teenagers. Opposing characteristics of behavior are manifested in the affection of loved ones, personal injury, fulfillment of demands. Actions in the opposite spirit are often aimed at parents and adults. When a problematic situation arises in the family, the child's inner and outer self manifests itself with minor or exaggerated violations. Such rebellious actions are caused by parents' indifference to the child, disrespect for him as a person, and hindering his interests. The reason for this is the parents' high demands on their children, their dreams of making him a prodigy - a person who achieves great heights. Concealing the feeling of enmity, the teenager shows his displeasure, frustration, alienation from adults. He begins to look for friends outside and often joins a group of drinkers and smokers.

V. The feeling of development (emancipation) is a teenager's struggle for his freedom and independence. He wants to be released from adult control as soon as possible. The more he is controlled, the more freedom he craves. To adults, he deliberately shows independent actions. If parents or teachers did not force him to do something, he would have done it voluntarily. This is due to the stubbornness of the teenager. Over time, mentally healthy teenagers go through extreme stubbornness. If adults demand extreme brutality and unconditional obedience, then teenagers show extreme character. The most alarming thing is that the behavior of teenagers in such cases ends with running away from home and becoming a nanny.

VI. Rejection is the feeling of being denied participation in games, eating, housework, and social activities. In this reality, parents refuse to communicate with some of their peers. In order to protect their child from drinking and smoking peers, parents are forced to move to another school, to another area, as a result, the teenager accuses his parents of separating him from his peers and complains about them.

REFERENCES:

1. Исакова, М. Т. "ЭМПИРИЧЕСКОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ОТНОШЕНИЯ ЛИЧНОСТИ К ЗДОРОВЬЮ С ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНО-ДИНАМИЧЕСКИМИ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАМИ." П 86 Психология управления персоналом и экосистема наставничества в условиях изменения технологического уклада. Вторая международная научно (2021): 544.

2. ИСАКОВА М. Т. СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ (УЗБЕКИСТАН) // СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ (УЗБЕКИСТАН) Учредители: Общество с

ограниченной ответственностью" Центр инновационных технологий". – №. 8. – С. 45-52.

3. ИСАКОВА, М. Т. СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ (УЗБЕКИСТАН). СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ (УЗБЕКИСТАН) Учредители: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью" Центр инновационных технологий", (8), 45-52.

4. Isaqova M. T. Etnopsixologiya //Toshkent: Iqbol-Turon. – 2007.

5. Usmonov S. A. OPPORTUNITIES WITH WORKING ABILITY CHILDREN IN EDUCATION //Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества. – 2020. – С. 298-300.

6. Usmonov S. A. PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS WITH WORKING ABILITY CHILDREN //Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества. – 2020. – С. 177-179.

7. Usmonov S. A., Xoldaraliyeva A. A. Q. TALABA YOSHLARNI TOLERANTLIK RUHIDA TARBIYALASHNING PSIXOLOGIK TAMOILLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 73-77.

8. Усмонов Ш. А., Закирова М. С., Нуриддинов Р. С. Ў. ИЛК ЎСПИРИНЛИК ДАВРИДА АКЎИЙ ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЭМПИРИК ТАҲЛИЛИ //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 9 (106). – С. 12-16.

9. Axmadjonovich U. S. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS ON MASTERY INDICATORS IN STUDENTS. – 2022.

10. Usmanov S., Absalomov E. U. IMPROVEMENT OF TOLERANT CULTURE IN THE FAMILY //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 674-676.

11. Soliev F. S., Muminov D. To determine individual specificity and hidden potential of the personality according to external signs of behavior //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 5. – С. 1258-1265.

12. Soliev, F. S., and D. Muminov. "To determine individual specificity and hidden potential of the personality according to external signs of behavior." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11.5 (2021): 1258-1265.

13. Soliev, F. S., & Muminov, D. (2021). To determine individual specificity and hidden potential of the personality according to external signs of behavior. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(5), 1258-1265.

14. МУМИНОВ Д. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА И

СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ //Uzbek Scholar Journal. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 60-62.

15. Муминов, Даврон. "ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА И СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ." Uzbek Scholar Journal 4 (2022): 60-62.

16. Муминов, Д. (2022). ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА И СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ. Uzbek Scholar Journal, 4, 60-62.

17. Ostanakulov A.D The history and role of Islam and psychology in the education system in Central Asia. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions <https://RESEARCHJET.ACADEMIASCIENCE.ORG> ISSN: 2776-0960 Impact Factor: 7.655 V O L U M E 2, I S S U E 4, A P R I L - 2 0 2 1

18. Джухонова Н. Х., Иброхимов Д. Этнопсихологические особенности подготовки девушек-студенток к семейной жизни //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 829-835.

19. Солиев, Ф. С., Абдуллаева, А. Р., & Джухонова, Н. Х. (2019). Формирование психологической культуры и этноценностных ориентаций студенческой молодежи. In Психологическое благополучие современного человека (pp. 334-339).

20. Djuxonova N. X., Mamajonova SH. Mahalla-qizlarni oilaviy hayotga tayyorlashning muhim omili sifatida //innovatsii v pedagogike i psixologii. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 7.

21. Djuxonova N. BADIY ADABIYOTLARDA PSIXOLINGVISTIKANING QO ‘LLANILISHI //Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6.

22. Djuxonova, Nohida. "BADIY ADABIYOTLARDA PSIXOLINGVISTIKANING QO ‘LLANILISHI." Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики 2.6 (2021).

23. Djuxonova, N. (2021). BADIY ADABIYOTLARDA PSIXOLINGVISTIKANING QO ‘LLANILISHI. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 2(6).

24. Джухонова Н. Х., Иброхимов Д. ЭТНОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВУШЕК-СТУДЕНТОК К СЕМЕЙНОЙ ЖИЗНИ //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 829-835.

25. Джухонова, Нохида Хаётжоновна, and Дониёр Иброхимов. "ЭТНОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВУШЕК-СТУДЕНТОК К СЕМЕЙНОЙ ЖИЗНИ." Scientific progress 2.4 (2021): 829-835.

26. Джухонова, Н. Х., & Иброхимов, Д. (2021). ЭТНОПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОДГОТОВКИ ДЕВУШЕК-СТУДЕНТОК К СЕМЕЙНОЙ ЖИЗНИ. Scientific progress, 2(4), 829-835.

27. Солиев Ф. С., Абдуллаева А. Р., Джухонова Н. Х. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ЭТНОЦЕННОСТНЫХ ОРИЕНТАЦИЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ //Психологическое благополучие современного человека. – 2019. – С. 334-339.

28. Солиев, Фарходжон Содикович, Арофатхон Рустамовна Абдуллаева, and Нохида Хаётжоновна Джухонова. "ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ЭТНОЦЕННОСТНЫХ ОРИЕНТАЦИЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ." Психологическое благополучие современного человека. 2019.

29. Солиев, Ф. С., Абдуллаева, А. Р., & Джухонова, Н. Х. (2019). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ЭТНОЦЕННОСТНЫХ ОРИЕНТАЦИЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ. In Психологическое благополучие современного человека (pp. 334-339).

30. Eleonora Topvoldieva Mirzajonova, Odinaxon Rahmanovna Parpiyeva //Modern Special Preschool Education: Problems and Solutions// Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. Vol. 9. 06-2022. 100-106 page.